

Negative sequence current injection by power electronics based generators and its impact on faulted phase selection algorithms of distance protection

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Abstract—Continuously increasing connection of Renewable Generators using Power Electronics (PE) in transmission and distribution levels has raised the interest of utilities to assess the impact of these devices on the protection systems currently installed in substations. Traditional protection systems have been so far developed for systems where short-circuit current sources are synchronous generators. The response of a synchronous generator during short circuit faults is well-known and widely described in literature [1]. The response of PE-based generators or HVDC links is based on the control strategies developed by manufacturers considering grid codes imposed by utilities or specific requirements applicable for specific projects. The response of PE devices differ from the well-known response of synchronous generators and could cause difficulties for certain protection functions like fault detection.

Work Package 4 of the MIGRATE project, a 4-year EU funded project that started in 2016, is dealing with the assessment of the behavior of protection systems in scenarios with high penetration of PE. Closed loop RTDS simulations have been performed in order to test the behavior of protection devices from four different manufacturers.

During the performed tests, it was noted that negative sequence control on PE-based generators has a strong impact on power system protection, which is relevant, considering that the latest network codes released by ENTSO-e include the possibility of establishing requirements for negative sequence current injection. This article is focused on the impact of negative sequence control on the behavior of faulted phase selection algorithms based on the comparison of the angle of negative sequence and zero sequence currents and superimposed quantities, and how different negative sequence control strategies affect its behavior.

Index Terms—future power systems, H2020, MIGRATE, power system protection, real time testing, power electronics

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I. INTRODUCTION

The use of power electronics in power system networks is a fact that for many years has played a key role in the transition to a more versatile and sustainable energy model.

Its use is increasingly becoming an option to facilitate the integration of renewable energies and long transmission corridors that rely on the use of power electronics as HVDC links, as well as a key element in the proliferation of distributed energy resources, the introduction of the electric vehicle, etc. Different applications of PE help to carry out an optimal management of the generation and consumption together with a reduction in power system losses through better distribution of power flows leading to a more responsible and sustainable use of natural resources.

However, despite the fact that the use of renewable energy generation technologies is an improvement from the environmental point of view, this penetration of power electronics also involves a significant change in the way of dimensioning and operating power systems, creating the necessity of redefining some foundations that are no longer valid in an environment where the presence of traditional synchronous generation has a lower weight over the total amount of generation.

In particular, this article aims to analyze in detail the impact of a certain type of PE based generator, commonly employed in full converter wind turbines and photovoltaic generators, in two commercial relays that are currently being installed in transmission networks and propose different alternatives to improve the performance of the distance protection function. With this objective, a study network has been established and relays are located in both sides of a line, in which one of the

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ends only has short circuit contribution from a type 4 wind turbine. A methodology for evaluating the performance of the distance protection function has been developed in [2] in order to verify if present levels of protection system dependability remain invariable in this new scenario or additional measures must be considered.

II. REAL TIME SIMULATION PLATFORM

In order to assess the impact of the negative sequence reactive injection, extensive simulations have been carried out with RTDS, using hardware in the loop test (HiL). The configuration is the same as the one used in WP4 Migrate project [2], a simplified scheme of the set up can be seen in Fig 1. The set-up is composed of a time real simulator (RTDS), voltage and current amplifiers and protection devices.

Fig 1. Hardware in the loop testing. Laboratory test-bench and signals exchanged [3]

For achieving this goal, a benchmark model has been developed, based on the one proposed by IEEE PRSC for protection relay testing and simulation in [4]. The final grid model debugged in RTDS is shown in Fig 2. It includes conventional synchronous generators, an HVDC link based on two level voltage source converters connecting bus 2 and 3, a photovoltaic generator, a full converter wind turbine and a Doubly Fed Induction Generator (DFIG) wind turbine.

Fig 2. Benchmark model developed in Migrate WP4

To analyze the behavior of faulted phase selection on distance protection when the only source of current behind the relay is a wind farm with full converter wind turbines (FCWT), two scenarios of installed generation capacity were considered: with installed power of 40 MW and with 200 MW.

The relays under test that were connected to the RTDS platform are two commercial ones with different phase selection algorithms: algorithm A, based on comparison between the angle of measured negative and zero sequence currents and algorithm B, based on superimposed quantities. Both algorithms are explained in section III. Furthermore, the two negative sequence control strategies considered in the study are negative sequence current suppression (strategy 1) and negative sequence current injection (strategy 3), these strategies are explained in section IV.

The methodology followed to assess the performance of the relays when the only source of short-circuit current behind them is a full converter turbine, has been the same as the one adopted in MIGRATE WP4 [2] [5] [6]. Numerous tests have been performed in line 5-7, where various fault types (SLG, LL, LLG) were applied (three times each) at different locations of the line: 0%, 50%, 70%, 90% and 100%. Results obtained for three phase faults have not been included in this paper as their adequate identification, in these scenarios, depends more on the current level and memory voltages than by the faulted phase selection algorithm. Additionally, present grid codes allow temporal disconnections of the PE based generators leading to non-injection of currents if voltages at the PCC are under a defined value (around 0.05 p.u.).

In order to automatically perform the tests, a RTDS script file has been specifically designed to apply the different types of faults and gather the results making use of Excel spreadsheets so as to determine the cases which required further analysis.

It is important to note that the two relays connected at both sides of line 5-7 are installed in parallel. The logic implemented in RTDS is based on the fact that unless the two relay trip, the breaker does not open. Therefore, it is necessary that both protections detect the fault to open the breaker and clear the fault. This implemented logic is necessary to analyze the different tripping times of the relays under study.

III. STATE OF THE ART OF FAULTED PHASE SELECTION ALGORITHMS

As it was previously mentioned, within WP4 of the MIGRATE project, closed loop tests with RTDS have been made, considering scenarios with synchronous generators and scenarios with high penetration of PE. Although the 4 different manufacturers have shown different behaviors during tests, all of them have experienced difficulties for correctly operating in scenarios with high penetration of PE [5] [6] when distance protection without communication was the main protection function and type 4 wind turbine was the only source feeding the short-circuit behind their location. One of the elements that has strong impact in this wrong behavior is the faulted phase selection algorithm employed by each manufacturer.

This section analyzes the state of the art of faulted phase selection algorithms. This analysis serves as an input for section

V which analyzes, from a theoretical point of view, the expected behavior of the different faulted phase selection algorithms for each of the negative sequence control strategies proposed.

As these algorithms were designed considering a power system in which the 100% of the generation was synchronous, the assumptions made during this section considers this scenario. Nevertheless, as it is demonstrated later in the article, the new scenario with PE based generators has strong impact into the behavior of these algorithms.

A. Comparison between the angle of measured negative and zero sequence current [7] [8] [9]

This algorithm determines the faulted phases by comparing the angles of the measured negative and zero sequence currents referenced to A-phase [7]. As it can be deduced from the following figure IA0 and IA2 are in phase for AG faults and their phase do not differ significantly for BCG faults.

Fig 3. Sequence components equivalent circuits for AG and BCG faults without Rf

Taking A-phase as reference for sequence quantities, IA2 lags IA0 for BG and CAG faults and IA2 leads IA0 for CG and ABG faults. Taking this into consideration, this algorithm creates sectors that allows to determine the fault type.

Increasing the Rf does not have impact in the angular difference for single line-to-ground faults as this resistance (multiplied by three) is in series with positive, negative and zero sequence impedances. However Rf increases this angle for double phase-to-ground faults, especially when this resistance is applied between the two phases and the ground. This is due to the fact that fault resistance is applied on the zero sequence branch multiplied by three, having less impact when the resistance is applied between the phases.

Fig 4. Sequence components equivalent for single line to ground and double phase to ground faults with fault resistance

When the angle between IA2 and IA0 is more than 30 degrees, the algorithm considers an additional criterion in order to ensure a reliable fault type identification. This additional criterion is based on the calculation of the fault resistance made for each fault loop, choosing single line to

ground fault loop or double phase to ground fault loop depending on which of them calculates the lowest value of resistance. For a BCG fault with a value of Rf that causes an angular difference of more than 30° between IA0 and IA2, the values of $|R_{ag}|$ and $|R_{bc}|$ are calculated according to (1) and (2). As a result of this calculation it is determined that $|R_{ag}|$ is larger than $|R_{bc}|$, leading to the declaration of BC type fault.

$$R_{ag} = \frac{Im \left[V_a \cdot \left((I_a + k_0 \cdot I_r) \cdot e^{jZ1ang} \right)^* \right]}{Im \left[\frac{3}{2} \cdot (I_{a2} + I_0) \cdot \left((I_a + k_0 \cdot I_r) \cdot e^{jZ1ang} \right)^* \right]} \quad (1)$$

$$R_{bc} = \frac{Im [V_{bc} \cdot (I_{bc} \cdot e^{jZ1ang})^*]}{Im [(j2 \cdot \sqrt{3} \cdot I_{a2}) \cdot (I_{bc} \cdot e^{jZ1ang})^*]} \quad (2)$$

Different approaches based on the comparison of negative and zero sequence magnitudes are used by other manufacturers. Some of them consider a different angular limit [10], while others calculate ratios between positive, negative and zero sequence magnitudes and include them in multi-criteria algorithms [11].

B. Superimposed Current Phase Selector [12] [13]

This algorithm makes use of superimposed currents for selecting the type of fault. Subtracting the value of the current before a change from the value after the change, the algorithm produces a signal that represents the change.

After a fault type selection only the elements associated with the selection are allowed to operate during 2 cycles. If no element operates during that time all elements are enabled for the following 5 cycles. If any element operates during these periods the phase selector state is frozen until the elements resets except for a change in the phase selection decision.

The algorithm calculates three phase-to-phase superimposed currents ($\Delta I_{ab}, \Delta I_{bc}, \Delta I_{ca}$). These currents are calculated by subtracting the phase to phase current sample taken 2 cycles earlier from present sample, in order to consider that a superimposed current has to be considered in the phase selection algorithm. Its value has to be at least 80% of the highest superimposed current considering that at least one of the superimposed currents exceeds a certain value relative to the nominal current.

Fig 5. Phase to phase currents change for CG fault [13]

It can be demonstrated that, for a single-phase-to-ground

fault, similar superimposed current is produced in two of the signals obtaining a lower value for the third one. For a phase-to-phase or double phase-to-ground fault one signal will be significantly larger than the others. Finally, for a three-phase fault the three quantities have similar values. A summary of the results can be seen in TABLE I.

TABLE I

VALUE OF INCREMENTAL CURRENTS FOR EACH TYPE OF FAULT

	Type of fault						
	AG	BG	CG	AB or ABG	BC or BCG	CA or CAg	ABC
ΔI_{ab}	H	H	L	H	L	L	H
ΔI_{bc}	L	H	H	L	H	L	H
ΔI_{ca}	H	L	H	L	L	H	H

Note: H= High value, L= Low value

C. Combined directional and faulted phase selector element based on incremental voltages and currents [14]

This algorithm determines the type of the fault based on the calculation of three scalar products involving six incremental quantities (incremental voltages and currents). The three scalar product are:

$$\Delta \overline{Z}_{AB} = \frac{\Delta \overline{V}_{AB}}{\Delta \overline{I}_{AB}} = \frac{\overline{V}_{AB_{POST}} - \overline{V}_{AB_{PRE}}}{\overline{I}_{AB_{POST}} - \overline{I}_{AB_{PRE}}} = -\overline{Z}_{S1} \quad (3)$$

$$\Delta \overline{Z}_{BC} = \frac{\Delta \overline{V}_{BC}}{\Delta \overline{I}_{BC}} = \frac{\overline{V}_{BC_{POST}} - \overline{V}_{BC_{PRE}}}{\overline{I}_{BC_{POST}} - \overline{I}_{BC_{PRE}}} = -\overline{Z}_{S1} \quad (4)$$

$$\Delta \overline{Z}_{CA} = \frac{\Delta \overline{V}_{CA}}{\Delta \overline{I}_{CA}} = \frac{\overline{V}_{CA_{POST}} - \overline{V}_{CA_{PRE}}}{\overline{I}_{CA_{POST}} - \overline{I}_{CA_{PRE}}} = -\overline{Z}_{S1} \quad (5)$$

In (3), (4), (5), \overline{Z}_{S1} is the calculated positive sequence impedance behind the relay. The equation (3) can be rewritten as:

$$\frac{\Delta \overline{V}_{AB}}{\Delta \overline{I}_{AB} \cdot (-\overline{Z}_{S1})} = 1 \quad (6)$$

From (6) it can be extracted that the product of the incremental current factor and the negative of the source positive sequence impedance has the same angle as the incremental voltage. By performing the following scalar product, direction of the fault can be deduced, as it has a positive sign for forward faults and negative sign for reverse ones:

$$\Delta \overline{V}_{AB}^{\circ} [\Delta \overline{I}_{AB} \cdot (-\overline{Z}_{S1})] = \text{Re}\{\Delta \overline{V}_{AB} \cdot [\Delta \overline{I}_{AB} \cdot (-\overline{Z}_{S1})]^*\} \quad (7)$$

In this algorithm it is assumed that the source impedance behind the relay is constant, thus the scalar product is reduced to:

$$\overline{Z}_{S1} = Z_{S1} \cdot e^{j\theta_{Z_{S1}}} \quad (8)$$

$$\overline{Z}_{S1} = Z_{S1} \cdot e^{j\theta_{Z_{S1}}} \quad (9)$$

$$\Delta \overline{T}_{AB} = \Delta \overline{V}_{AB}^{\circ} [-\Delta \overline{I}_{ABC}]^* = \text{Re}\{\Delta \overline{V}_{AB}\} \cdot \text{Re}\{-\Delta \overline{I}_{ABC}\} + \text{Im}\{\Delta \overline{V}_{AB}\} \cdot \text{Im}\{-\Delta \overline{I}_{ABC}\} \quad (10)$$

For this algorithm it can be demonstrated that TABLE I is substituted by TABLE II, which in fact is similar but includes additional information as the direction of the fault:

TABLE II

SCALAR PRODUCTS IN INCREMENTAL IMPEDANCE ALGORITHM [14]

	Type of fault						
	AG	BG	CG	AB or ABG	BC or BCG	CA or CAg	ABC
ΔT_{ab}	ΔT_{ab}	ΔT_{ab}	0	ΔT_{ab}	$0,25 \cdot \Delta T_{bc}$	$0,25 \cdot \Delta T_{ca}$	ΔT_{ab}
ΔT_{bc}	0	ΔT_{ab}	ΔT_{bc}	$0,25 \cdot \Delta T_{ab}$	ΔT_{bc}	$0,25 \cdot \Delta T_{ca}$	ΔT_{ab}
ΔT_{ca}	ΔT_{ab}	0	ΔT_{bc}	$0,25 \cdot \Delta T_{ab}$	$0,25 \cdot \Delta T_{bc}$	ΔT_{ca}	ΔT_{ab}

D. Multi-criteria algorithms

Multi-criteria algorithms are those which take into consideration two or more algorithms for determining the faulted phase [11]. While some of them could take the decision based on the agreement between the results of the calculations of at least two of the algorithms, others include some kind of weighting or priority rule for selecting which is the most accurate one for each grid condition. A multi-criteria algorithm could be based on current or voltage levels, delta current or delta voltages, impedance calculations, symmetrical components, jump detections...

E. Experimental methods

Various experimental or innovative methods can be found in literature, such as Stockwell Transform (S-Transform) [15] [16], Wavelet transform and artificial intelligence [17], or travelling waves [18] [19] among others. As the purpose of this article is to determine the impact of PE based generators on present power system protections, an extensive explanation of these algorithms is not provided. Nevertheless further work can be done for assessing the impact PE controls on these algorithms, especially considering promising methods that are currently being introduced in the market with commercial relevancy as the travelling waves one.

IV. NEGATIVE SEQUENCE CONTROL STRATEGIES IN PE BASED GENERATORS

In this section, different possible negative sequence control strategies applicable in PE based generators during unbalanced faults is discussed. Some of them are already implemented in PE based generators (strategies 1 and 2) while other (strategy 3) are included in the study with the intention of assessing their benefits and serve as base for future requirements. These

strategies cover negative sequence current suppression strategy, which represents the most problematic for present faulted phase selection algorithm and other strategies in which a certain amount of negative sequence current is injected by PE generators during unbalanced faults, based on negative sequence voltage instantaneous value.

Negative sequence current control strategy interacts with other control strategies included in the network codes such as fault-ride-through or voltage support (positive sequence reactive power) due to the total limitation of current according to the features of the PE. It is out of the scope of this article to analyze the impact between these control strategies but, before defining a solid requirement, technical discussions between utilities and PE manufacturers should be carried out in order to avoid the risk of establishing technically unattainable requirements.

Considering the behavior of the PE based generator after a fault inception, despite the control strategy chosen, six stages can be easily distinguished from the initial steady state until a new steady state after the clearance of the fault. These stages can be summarized as:

- Initial steady state: During this stage the PE based generator controls, follow steady state control strategies, maximizing active power injection and providing voltage support if required by the network code of the utility where it is connected.
- Fault inception: This stage could last 7-20 ms and occurs just after the fault inception. During this period controls have not reacted yet to the new conditions of the network, activating the strategies applicable for disturbances.
- Transition period: The PE based generator controls have detected the fault condition and have activated the fault condition strategy. During this period, that could last between 20 to 40 ms, the control system progressively modifies the fault current contribution provided by the renewable source. The time response of this transition period depends on the programmed control strategies (FRT, voltage support, negative sequence current control, etc) and the dynamics of the control system.
- Steady state fault contribution: During this stage, which lasts until the clearance of the fault or the disconnection of the PE (if the fault is not cleared within the time established in the FRT characteristic depending on the severity of the fault), the PE based generator provides total control of the currents injected with a maximum value of current of around 1.1-1.3 p.u.
- Fault clearance: After the fault is cleared, the control system faces a new period when it firstly detects that the fault has been cleared and then progressively adapts the currents injected to the new grid condition.
- Final steady state: The PE based generator reaches a new stable steady state activating again strategies related with the maximization of active power injection and voltage support.

A. Strategy 1: Negative sequence current suppression

This control strategy leads to symmetrical current injection either for balanced or unbalanced faults during the steady state period of the fault. Previously to reach this steady state period, PE based generators experience a transition period. During this period, a certain amount of unbalance between phase currents will be observed, but the control progressively damps this unbalance until a balanced current output is achieved.

The response of the PE based generator with this control strategy is governed by the LVRT requirements that avoids the disconnection of the converter and, if required by the utility, it injects positive sequence reactive current. In [20] a control in which a positive sequence capacitive current proportional to the positive sequence voltage drop is required, considering a non-injection band of 10% is explained:

$$i_{q+} = k_+(0.9 - V_+) \quad (11)$$

Fig 6. LVRT positive sequence reactive current injection in Germany [21]

However, this control strategy has certain drawbacks that must be considered. The injection of a symmetrical reactive current (following the Grid Code requirements) during unbalanced faults can lead to severe overvoltages in the healthy phases during unbalanced faults [22]. Additionally, a symmetrical current injection during unbalanced faults causes traditional power system protection devices to fail to detect the fault or correctly identify the faulted phases when PE based generators are the only short-circuit current source as it is analyzed in Migrate project WP4 [2].

B. Strategy 2: German Grid Code

This strategy is explained in detail in [21]. It aims to avoid the balanced reactive current injection explained in the first strategy. In order to achieve this goal, negative sequence reactive current injection is required so as to provide an adequate grid support either for symmetrical and asymmetrical faults.

This control strategy considers the profile observed in Fig 6 for the injection of positive sequence capacitive current and Fig 7 for the injection of negative sequence inductive current. As it can be seen, a non-injection band of 5% is considered as well in this strategy and the negative sequence inductive current can be calculated with (12) where V_- is the negative sequence voltage in p.u.

The initial time, rise time and settling time required in this control strategy are the same as in strategy 3.

$$i_{q-} = k_-(V_- - 0.05) \quad (12)$$

Fig 7. LVRT negative sequence reactive current injection in Germany [21]

C. Strategy 3: MIGRATE project WP4 Full Converter Negative sequence control strategy

During 2016, in the first year of work of Working Package 4 of the MIGRATE project, a flexible negative sequence control strategy was implemented in the detailed Full Converter Wind Turbine model [3]. This strategy is able of operating either suppressing negative sequence current for unbalanced faults or injecting a certain amount of negative sequence current during these faults. This flexible model allows verifying the behavior of traditional protection devices with the strategy of negative sequence current suppression and also allows to perform a first assessment of the potential improvement of their behavior considering a certain amount of negative sequence current.

In order to inject negative sequence current, the control strategy splits the positive and negative sequence current and voltage control loops in order to control the positive and negative active and reactive power injected by the PE. The aim of the controls implemented is to emulate the response of a synchronous generator during unbalanced faults based on negative sequence network. Additionally, the control system limits the currents injected in amplitude due to the physical limitations imposed by the converters.

Once the calculated positive sequence voltage goes below 0.9 p.u., the control enters in the voltage support working mode. The voltage support control strategy is based on the one defined by Tennet GmbH in [23].

When the control enters in fault mode, the total and reactive current delivered by the PE based generator before the fault are stored. The control then calculates the increment of reactive current needed considering the strategy included in [23] and considering the maximum current allowed for the converter. Finally it calculates the active current to inject considering the increment of reactive current needed and the current limit.

Fig 8. Voltage support control strategy during disturbances [23]

The negative sequence control strategy proposed, is based on the negative sequence network of synchronous generator. Control system measures the negative sequence voltage and it is designed to inject a negative sequence current proportional to this measured voltage, with the idea of emulating the behavior of synchronous generator, based on its negative sequence network. In order to achieve it, the following steps are needed:

- Measurement of negative sequence voltage U_{neg}
- Calculation of negative sequence current I_{neg} with:

$$I_{neg} = k \cdot U_{neg} \quad (13)$$

- The negative sequence current is limited according to the maximum current limit. This maximum is shared between the positive and negative sequence current. The injection of negative sequence reactive current limits the amount of positive sequence reactive current that can be injected. Despite this is the most severe condition that can be established for this limitation as it is explained in [22], for the simulations included in this paper the condition stated in (14) is considered.

$$|i_1| + |i_2| \leq i_{max} \quad (14)$$

- Once the apparent power is calculated for the negative sequence, active and reactive power are calculated with a power factor selectable by the user. This power factor could allow the user to distribute the apparent power into different amount of active and reactive power in negative sequence.

In order to complete the definition of the control strategy considering the stages explained at the beginning of this section, the following time responses must be defined:

- Initial time (**ti**): The maximum delay for the beginning of the injection/ consumption of current after the occurrence of a disturbance is 20 ms.
- Rise time (**tr**): Maximum time between the start of injection/ consumption of current until the PE generator reaches 90% of the target is 30 ms.
- Settling time (**te**): Maximum time between the start of the injection/ consumption of current until the response is within a band of $\pm 5\%$ of the target is 60 ms.

Fig 9. Time response requirements for the injection/ consumption of fast fault currents.

In the next sections a theoretical analysis of the impact of the previous strategy for different types of faults considering symmetrical components theory, are shown.

It must be noted as well that, for injecting reactive negative sequence current during disturbances, a minimum time between 5-10 ms is required for a reliable estimation of negative sequence voltage angle. This estimation needs a certain magnitude of negative sequence voltage that could be fixed around 0.05 p.u [22].

Fig 10. Voltages at PCC during a phase to phase fault

Fig 11. Currents injected by a PE based generator with negative sequence current suppression strategy with the model developed in MIGRATE WP4

Fig 12. Currents injected by a PE based generator with negative sequence current injection ($k=2$) strategy with the model developed in MIGRATE WP4 considering active and reactive negative sequence current injection.

V. THEORETICAL ANALYSIS OF THE IMPACT OF DIFFERENT NEGATIVE SEQUENCE CONTROL STRATEGIES IN FAULTED PHASE SELECTION ALGORITHMS

In order to proceed with the theoretical analysis of the impact of the different negative sequence control strategies in faulted phase selection algorithms, a brief explanation of the Grid Side Converter (GSC) control included in the full converter wind turbine model developed for the study is needed.

In a full converter wind turbine, short circuit contribution is driven by the GSC control. Fig 13 shows the block diagram of GSC control developed in MIGRATE project [3]:

Fig 13. Grid Side Converter Control (GSC) developed for the MIGRATE Project [3]

The positive and negative decomposition block is in charge of providing to the positive and negative sequence control block the measured currents and voltages after applying the corresponding ABC/ DQ transformation. Once $I_d(+)$, $I_q(+)$, $I_d(-)$ and $I_q(-)$ are introduced in the positive and negative sequence control block it compares their values against the references imposed by its control strategy.

Positive sequence control loop is in charge of the control of active power (P) and reactive power (Q) injection. Under

healthy steady state conditions in AC grid, P control is fixed by the voltage in the DC Bus (U_{dc}) and its reference value ($U_{dc,ref}$), and Q is fixed by the AC voltage in the converter filter (U_{ac}) and its reference value ($U_{ac,ref}$).

In case of a fault in the AC grid, the control system switches to fault mode to provide P and Q active and reactive current according to grid code requirements.

Negative sequence current control ($I_{2CONTROL LOOP}$) is in charge of the negative sequence current (I_2) injection. Under healthy steady state conditions in the AC grid, the control strategy suppresses I_2 . Despite in a healthy balanced system a certain value of U_2 always exists, its value is low and it can be neglected. This control does not operate during healthy conditions, reducing the interactions of this control strategy during normal undisturbed conditions.

In case of fault in AC grid, I_2 injection is determined by the control strategy implemented. As the control developed in the MIGRATE project is flexible to select between two different control strategies based on I_2 suppression or I_2 injection, this theoretical analysis has been developed for control strategy 1 and control strategy 3.

In order to model the full converter wind turbine in case of unbalanced faults in sequence networks, three different periods have been identified:

A. Period 1: Initial Time.

This period is comprised between fault inception to positive and negative sequence control response.

Fault detection is based on positive sequence voltage (V_1) dip. When V_1 is below the positive sequence voltage reference ($V_{1,Ref}$), fault detection mode is activated, and I_1 and I_2 injection is established by control strategies implemented and their control dynamics. Therefore period 1 duration is fixed by fault detection time and PI regulators response times:

$$InitialTime = T_{FaultDetection} + MinTime \begin{cases} T_{PSC_{id}} \\ T_{PSC_{iq}} \\ T_{NSC_{id}} \\ T_{NSC_{iq}} \end{cases} \quad (15)$$

Where $T_{FaultDetection}$ is the time response of fault detection mode, $T_{PSC_{id}}$ and $T_{PSC_{iq}}$ are the time responses of positive sequence Id and Iq control loops and $T_{NSC_{id}}$ and $T_{NSC_{iq}}$ are the time responses of negative sequence Id and Iq control loops. The control signals produced by the four control loops are $md(+)$, $mq(+)$, $md(-)$ and $mq(-)$ and after a DQ/ABC transformation, they are traduced into IGBT firing pulses.

Fig 14. Active, reactive and negative sequence current control loops [3]

Once the fault detection mode is activated, the four control loops for managing positive and negative sequence are PI controls with transfer functions that can be expressed as:

$$G_c(s) = \frac{K_p(1 + T_i s)}{s} \quad (16)$$

These PI regulators provide a dynamic that introduces a delay in the response, depending on proportional (K_p) and integral (T_i) parameters, the own dynamic of the system due to its proper impedances and error signals $I_{x0}(t)$.

Action magnitudes for each control loop can be expressed as:

$$m_{x0}(t) = K_p I_{x0}(t) + 1/T_i \int_t^{t+T_i} I_{x0}(t) dt \quad (17)$$

Note that both the proportional and the integral terms of the expression determine the action of the control and, therefore, the time response of the control loops.

During the first milliseconds after the fault inception, until the positive and the negative sequence control loops generate actions to modify the IGBT firing pulses, the firing angle of the IGBT remains instantaneously the same as the pre-fault state.

As the DC voltage is constant during the fault period due to DC bus capacitor and the security DC chopper control system, the converter voltage output in the Period 1 can be considered to be the same as the pre-fault state.

According to these assumptions, during period 1, full converter wind turbine behavior can be considered as a voltage source with a pre-fault voltage output, and it can be considered that the behavior for this Period 1 is similar to a synchronous generator.

The aforementioned implies that during period 1 there is injection of the negative sequence current and, therefore, unbalanced currents. The value of positive and negative sequence impedances can be approximated by the value of the

reactance of the converter output filter plus a converter impedance as the converter cannot be an ideal voltage source.

Sequence networks for unbalanced faults are shown in the following figures:

Fig 15. Sequence networks for a line to line fault analysis during period 1.

Fig 16. Sequence networks for a line to line to ground fault analysis during period 1.

Fig 17. Sequence networks for the analysis of a single line to ground fault during period 1.

Currents injected during Period 1 are similar regardless of the control strategy chosen and they only depend on the type of fault and the time response of the positive and negative control loops. Period 1 can be considered as a natural transient response of the full converter wind turbine in case of grid fault.

B. Period 2: Rise Time.

Period 2 is defined by the time response of the positive and negative sequence controls until reaching the 90% of the active, reactive and negative sequence current targets defined by the corresponding grid code.

During this period, the four control loops of positive and negative sequence are modifying the firing angle of the IGBTs in order to reach the current reference values fixed by control reference during the fault mode.

During Period 2 it is difficult to calculate the sequence currents injected by the full converter wind turbine following traditional methods commonly employed by protection engineers, since the action of PI regulators experiences significant changes during this transient period and a deep knowledge of the time response of these PI regulators is needed. Control system calculates positive and negative current targets according to their reference values, that is, they determine which are the final modules and angles of I_{FC1} and I_{FC2} . PI regulators act to reduce the error of present values respect to the desired ones according with their time response.

As during this period the injection of I_{FC1} and I_{FC2} are governed by the combined response of the PI regulators of the four control loops previously explained, its analysis through symmetrical components is not suggested. As the dynamic of the controls is defined by integral equations, the current

injection provides oscillations both in magnitude and phase during the settling time, making difficult to predict its instantaneous value during this period. In this condition is not possible to reliably estimate phasors. In order to determine the magnitudes and phase of the currents injected during this period a detailed analysis of the dynamic response of the PI regulators might be performed.

C. Period 3: Fault Steady State.

In Period 3, I_1 and I_2 injected by the full converter wind turbine are close to the reference values, and they can be considered stable.

In the same way as Period 2, the sequence networks depend on the control strategies for I_1 and I_2 injection.

- Strategy 1 : Negative sequence current suppression:

In this strategy, $I_{2CONTROL LOOP}$ has suppressed I_2 . Hence, negative sequence network can be considered as an open circuit.

I_1 injected by full converter wind turbine has reached the reference value I_{LIMIT} . This positive sequence current includes the voltage support required by the grid code (reactive current) and, the rest of current up to the maximum thermal limit of the converter, is completed with active current. The sequence currents can be expressed as:

$$\underline{I_{FC1}} = \left[\left| \underline{I_{FC1 Period1}} \right| + |\Delta I_{FC1}| \right] \cdot e^{j(\varphi_{i1} + \Delta\varphi_{c1})} \quad (18)$$

$$\underline{I_{FC2}} = 0 \quad (19)$$

$$\left| \underline{I_{FC1}} \right| \leq I_{Limit} \quad (20)$$

Where:

ΔI_{FC1} is the required variation of the magnitude of $\underline{I_{FC1 Period1}}$ based on the control strategy

φ_{i1} is the initial value of the angle of $\underline{I_{FC1 Period1}}$

$\Delta\varphi_{c1}$ is the required variation of the angle of $\underline{I_{FC1 Period1}}$ based on the control strategy

- Strategy 3 :

The control loops for positive and negative sequence injection have reached the reference values, and the sequence current injected can be expressed as:

$$\underline{I_{FC1}} = \left[\left| \underline{I_{FC1 Period1}} \right| + |\Delta I_{FC1}| \right] \cdot e^{j(\varphi_{i1} + \Delta\varphi_{c1})} \quad (21)$$

$$\underline{I_{FC2}} = \left[\left| \underline{I_{FC2 Period1}} \right| + |\Delta I_{FC2}| \right] \cdot e^{j(\varphi_{i2} + \Delta\varphi_{c2})} \quad (22)$$

$$\left| \underline{I_{FC1}} + \underline{I_{FC2}} \right| \leq I_{Limit} \quad (23)$$

Where:

ΔI_{FC2} is the required variation of the magnitude of $\underline{I_{FC2 Period1}}$ based on the control strategy

$\Delta\varphi_{c2}$ is the required variation of the angle of $\underline{I_{FC2 Period1}}$

The sequence networks for Period 2 and Period 3 for unbalanced faults are shown in the next figures:

Fig 18. Sequence networks for the analysis of a line to line fault during period 3.

Fig 19. Sequence networks for the analysis of a line to line to ground fault during period 3.

Fig 20. Sequence networks for the analysis of a single line to ground fault during period 3.

Theoretical impact on faulted phase selection algorithms.

According to the explanation of the three different periods, it can be deduced that problems in faulted phase selection algorithms can arise during the fault:

- Period 1: Initial Time

As during this period the behavior is similar to a synchronous generator, algorithms mentioned in SECTION III are expected to work properly.

- Period 2: Rise Time

As mentioned previously in this section, during this period positive and negative sequence controls are acting in order to reach reference values of positive/negative active/reactive currents. Under these conditions, current waveforms differ from the traditional behavior of synchronous generator, and depend on the dynamics of the control and power systems, trying to follow the reference established with each strategy, which can lead to wrong faulted phase selection.

It can be noted that algorithms based on angle difference between I_0 and I_2 (SECTION III. A) are strongly influenced by the I_2 strategy. I_2 injection is supposed to improve the performance as well as a lack of I_2 affects negatively for a right faulted phase selection. Although I_2 injection can improve the performance of these algorithms, its correct performance during this period cannot be guaranteed, due to the current waveforms

that could appear due to the control and power system dynamics.

In case of algorithms based on Superimposed Current Quantities or Voltage and Current incremental quantities (SECTION III. B AND C), it can be deduced that they are affected negatively during this period, and can lead to wrong faulted phase selection as these algorithms are based on current and voltage changes when synchronous generation is injecting short circuit current, and during this period current waveforms are difficult to predict due to control dynamics.

- Period 3: Fault Steady State.

In this period, currents injected by Full Converter are stable and their magnitudes have reached their reference values.

In the same way as in Period 2, I_2 injection is supposed to improve the performance as well as a lack of I_2 affects negatively for a right faulty phase selection on algorithms based on I_0 and I_2 angle difference.

In case of algorithms based on Superimposed Current Quantities or Voltage and Current incremental quantities (Section III. B and C), control strategies based on I_2 suppression provides a negative impact in the performance as current injection is balanced for any type of fault. I_2 injection strategies can improve the performance as the current injection is unbalanced, but the level and specially the angle of the currents injected, could not be sufficient for the correct performance of these algorithms and could lead as well to increments in the currents that differ from those observed in traditional power systems with synchronous.

VI. REAL TIME TESTING RESULTS

In order to assess the impact of the negative sequence reactive injection, as it has been previously explained in section II, extensive simulations have been carried out with RTDS. Two commercial relays with different phase selection algorithms, comparison between the angle of measured negative and zero sequence current (Algorithm A) and superimposed quantities (Algorithm B), have been integrated into the RTDS platform. Their behavior during different types of faults (SLG, LL, LLG) when the only source of short-circuit current behind them is a full converter turbine has been assessed. The two strategies considered in the study are negative sequence current suppression (strategy 1) and negative sequence current injection (strategy 3) with a value of 3.5 for the k constant defined in (13). Two scenarios have been considered, one with a wind park with a total installed power of 40 MW and another with a total installed power of 200 MW. The Z1 and Z2 settings have been made considering instantaneous trip and 80% of line impedance for Z1 and 400 ms trip and 120% of line impedance for Z2. The results obtained have been summarized in Fig 21, Fig 22, Fig 23 and Fig 24.

Fig 21. Results obtained with control strategy 1 (Negative sequence current suppression) for faults located in Z1.

Fig 24. Results obtained with control strategy 1 (Negative sequence current injection) for faults located in Z2

Fig 22. Results obtained with control strategy 3 (Negative sequence current injection) for faults located in Z1

Fig 23. Results obtained with control strategy 1 (Negative sequence current suppression) for faults located in Z2

The results obtained show that negative sequence current injection has a huge impact in the relay behavior, improving its response. Even with negative sequence current injection, it is not possible to obtain good results in the scenario of the wind park of 40 MW with any of the algorithms. This is due to the fact of the limited current injection of type 4 wind turbines combined with the current transformers commonly employed in transmission systems, result in currents below the sensitivity of the transmission system relays, leading to non-operations. Nevertheless, considering that sufficient current for the operation of the relay algorithms is injected, negative sequence current injection improves the operation of the relays.

Being strategy 3 implemented in full converter, the relay with algorithm A has operated correctly in the 100% of the cases, only showing a 20% of delays in zone 1 with trips around 60 ms but without tripping delays above 100 ms or no trips. This behavior is justified, because when the fault appears there is a transition period in the controls of the PE based generator in which it tries to modify the current injection to adapt it to the requirement of negative sequence reactive current. Although initially the relay correctly determines the faulted phase, during this period there are a few cycles in which the relay has an incorrect faulted phase selection until it comes back to the initial correct fault selection and orders the trip as it can be seen in Fig 25. This behavior has been observed as well in the relay with algorithm B. In this relay has led as well to trip in Z1 for faults in Z2 because of a wrong faulted phase selection combined with some milliseconds of measured impedance in Z1.

Fig 25. Faulted phase selection algorithm of relay with algorithm A for a SLG fault in phase A

Next, the behaviors of relay A and B during SLG and LL faults, considering negative sequence current injection (Strategy 3) implemented in the full converter are explained in

detail. For this analysis the scenario with 200 MW will be considered.

- Relay A behavior during SLG fault (200 MW scenario)

During a SLG fault applied at the end of the line (BUS 5 in Fig 2), a relay located at bus 7 sees the currents of Fig 26.

Fig 26. Currents seen by a relay located at BUS 7 for a bolted AG fault at BUS 5

Analyzing the currents that appear in the first 50 ms after the fault inception (periods 1 and 2 as explained in SECTION V) and the behavior of the relay during this period, it can be seen that, both the magnitude and angle of I2 are being modified by the converter interfaced generator. Calculated I2 magnitude and angle experiences great changes during this period as it is showed in Fig 27, Fig 28 and Fig 29. During this period, faulted phase selection algorithm could not operate correctly leading to possible wrong operation of the relay.

Fig 27. Currents seen by a relay located at BUS 7 for a bolted AG fault at BUS 5 for $0 < t < 50$ ms

Fig 28. Calculated angle of I2 against I0 for $0 < t < 50$ ms (AG fault)

Fig 29. Calculated magnitudes of I2 and I1 for $0 < t < 50$ ms (AG fault)

Period 3 starts 50- 60 ms after the fault inception. When similar analysis of currents is carried out from 50 ms to the clearance of the fault, it can be seen that currents are totally controlled (Fig 30). Besides, the angle of I2 is kept inside the $\pm 30^\circ$ frame defined in the algorithm for AG or BC faults (Fig 31). Furthermore I2 and I1 magnitudes are not experiencing big variations (Fig 32) and measurement of fault resistance on AG loop and BC loop confirm the selection of AG fault type (Fig 33).

Fig 30. Currents seen by a relay located at BUS 7 for a bolted AG fault at BUS 5 for $t > 50$ ms

Fig 31. Calculated angle of I2 against I0 for $t > 50$ ms (AG fault)

Fig 32. Calculated magnitudes of I2 and I1 for $t > 50$ ms (AG fault)

Fig 33. Calculated magnitudes of Rag and Rbc for $t > 50$ ms (AG fault)

- Relay B behavior during SLG fault (200 MW scenario)

During the same SLG fault explained previously for relay A, relay B shows correct behavior with a trip in zone 2 time only showing a small delay in comparison with the tripping time of relay A. However, a deeper analysis of the oscillography of relay B, shows that the fault selector is unable to correctly determine the type of fault. The trip has been correct due to the internal logic of the relay which after two cycles following a fault type selection with no pickup of any distance element, releases all distance elements.

A brief theoretical analysis of the type of the fault that this algorithm will determine, based on the currents seen by the relay in this scenario during the first 80 ms, shows that, once the currents injected by the converter interfaced generator are stabilized, the relay incorrectly determines the fault type declaring a CA fault instead of an AG fault. Although this theoretical analysis (TABLE III) does not accurately represent the actual behavior of the relay, the conclusions of the analysis have been checked with the oscillography of the relay Fig 34, showing similar results thus leading to the same conclusions obtained with the theoretical analysis.

TABLE III

THEORETICAL FAULTED PHASE SELECTION OF RELAY B DURING SLG (AG) FAULT

t(ms)	Torque ab	Torque bc	Torque ca	Type of fault
0	+	-	-	AB
2,5	+	-	+	AG
5	+	-	-	AB
7,5	+	-	-	AB
10	+	-	-	AB
12,5	+	-	-	AB
15	+	-	+	AG
17,5	+	-	+	AG
20	+	-	-	AB
22,5	+	+	-	BG
25	+	-	-	AB
27,5	+	+	-	BG
30	+	+	-	BG
32,5	+	+	-	BG
35	+	+	-	BG
37,5	-	+	+	CG
40	-	-	+	CA
42,5	-	+	+	CG
45	-	+	+	CG
47,5	-	-	+	CA
50	-	-	+	CA
52,5	-	+	+	CG
55	-	-	+	CA
57,5	-	-	+	CA
60	-	-	+	CA
62,5	-	-	+	CA
65	-	-	+	CA
67,5	-	-	+	CA
70	-	-	+	CA
72,5	-	-	+	CA
75	-	-	+	CA
77,5	-	-	+	CA
80	-	-	+	CA

Fig 34. Faulted phase selection algorithm of relay with algorithm B for an AG fault in BUS 5

- Relay A behavior during LL fault (200 MW scenario)

During a LL fault applied at the end of the line (BUS 5 in Fig 2), a relay located at bus 7 sees the currents of Fig 35.

Fig 35. Currents seen by a relay located at BUS 7 for a bolted AB fault at BUS 5

Following a similar approach as the followed for the SLG for the LL fault during the first 50 ms after the fault inception (periods 1 and 2), it can be seen that, during this period the currents are being adjusted. There are great variations of both magnitude and angle of I2 and the values calculated for the AB, BC and CA loop impedances are varying (Fig 36, Fig 37, Fig 38 and Fig 39).

Fig 36. Currents seen by a relay located at BUS 7 for a bolted AB fault at BUS 5 for $0 < t < 50$ ms

Fig 37. Calculated angle of I2 against I1 for $0 < t < 50$ ms (AB fault)

Fig 38. Calculated magnitudes of I2 and I1 for $0 < t < 50$ ms (AB fault)

Fig 39. Impedance calculations for AB, CA and BC loops for $0 < t < 50$ ms (AB fault)

During period 3, total control over the currents is achieved, stabilizing magnitudes of I1, I2 and the angle between them,

leading to a stable calculation of the loop impedances (Fig 40, Fig 41, Fig 42 and Fig 43). Although it can be seen that the control is substantially slower than in the AG fault, correct Z2 trip of the AB loop is achieved.

Fig 40. Currents seen by a relay located at BUS 7 for a bolted AB fault at BUS 5 for $t > 50$ ms

Fig 41. Calculated angle of I2 against I1 for $t > 50$ ms (AB fault)

Fig 42. Calculated magnitudes of I2 and I1 for $t > 50$ ms (AB fault)

Fig 43. Impedance calculations for AB, CA and BC loops for $t > 50$ ms (AB fault)

- *Relay B behavior during LL fault (200 MW scenario)*

During the same LL fault explained previously for relay A, relay B shows good behavior with a trip in zone 2 time only showing a small delay related with the tripping time of relay A. A deeper analysis of the oscillography of the relay shows that this delay is due to wrong phase selection during a period comprised in the transient period where currents injected by the converter interfaced generator are being adjusted.

A theoretical analysis of the faulted phase selection algorithm identical to the one carried out previously for the SLG fault shows that, after the transient period in which wrong faulted phase selection could appear, the algorithm correctly determines the faulted phase.

TABLE IV

THEORETICAL FAULTED PHASE SELECTION OF RELAY B DURING LL (AB) FAULT

t(ms)	Torque ab	Torque bc	Torque ca	Type of fault
0	-	-	-	-
2,5	+	-	-	AB
5	+	-	-	AB
7,5	+	-	-	AB
10	+	-	-	AB
12,5	+	+	-	BG
15	+	-	-	AB
17,5	+	-	-	AB
20	+	+	-	BG
22,5	-	+	-	BC
25	-	+	-	BC
27,5	-	+	-	BC
30	-	+	-	BC
32,5	-	+	-	BC
35	-	+	+	CG
37,5	-	-	+	CA
40	-	-	+	CA
42,5	-	-	+	CA
45	-	-	+	CA
47,5	+	-	+	AG
50	+	-	+	AG
52,5	+	-	+	AG
55	+	-	+	AG
57,5	+	-	-	AB
60	+	-	-	AB
62,5	+	-	-	AB
65	+	-	-	AB
67,5	+	-	-	AB
70	+	-	-	AB
72,5	+	-	-	AB
75	+	-	-	AB
77,5	+	-	-	AB
80	+	-	-	AB
82,5	+	-	-	AB
85	+	-	-	AB
87,5	+	-	-	AB
90	+	-	-	AB

VII. CONCLUSIONS

Present article analyzes the impact of negative sequence current control in the faulted phase selection algorithm. Section II describes the platform employed for the study. Section III summarizes the state of the art of faulted phase selection algorithms specially the two algorithms included in the commercial relays that have been tested in the platform described. Section IV describes 3 negative sequence control strategies, one is negative sequence current suppression while the others establish a certain level of negative sequence current injection function of the negative sequence voltage at the PCC. Section V describes the applicable sequence networks of a full converter wind turbine for each period from fault inception to

steady state faulty period. It also analyzes the impact of each period in the faulted phase selection algorithms included in the two commercial relays under test. Finally, section VI presents the results obtained during the tests carried out with the simulation platform described.

The analysis performed, show that, the behavior of relays with algorithm A and B have better behavior when negative sequence injection control strategy is included in the converter-interfaced generators. Even with negative sequence current injection, although the results for the relay with strategy B are improved, this phase selection algorithm is unable to correctly detect the faulted phases for every type of fault with the control strategy proposed. This behavior is especially aggravated when the fault involves ground, showing correct behavior during LL faults after the transient period. The previous is mainly related with the shape and the magnitude of the currents when the PE generator is the only source of short-circuit current behind the relay. This leads to phase currents that differ from those obtained when a synchronous generator feeds the fault. This issue has a huge impact in the phase selection algorithm B.

The behavior observed leads to the recommendation of giving some temporization to Z1, in line with the response times established for the negative sequence control strategy. A temporization between 30-50 ms would be sufficient to avoid Z1 overreach. If the delay proposed for Z1 is not acceptable, line differential protection must be considered for ensuring instantaneous tripping.

Results obtained show that:

- Although the analysis with symmetrical components is still applicable in scenarios with high PE penetration, sequence networks depend on the instant of the study.
- Faulted phase selection algorithms are affected by negative sequence current injection requirements.
- Relays present a much better behavior when negative sequence current injection is included in the grid code and therefore included in PE control strategies.
- Algorithm A, based in the comparison of the angle of negative and zero sequence currents presented a good behavior in the scenario with negative sequence current injection requirement, having 100% acceptable trips.
- Algorithm B, showed better behavior in the scenario with a negative sequence current injection requirement. Nevertheless a deeper analysis of the oscillographies of the relay revealed that this algorithm is not able to correctly determine the faulted phases under all circumstances, especially during faults involving ground.
- A temporization of Z1, considering time response requirements of PE based generators included in the applicable grid code, must be considered for scenarios where these types of generators could be the only source of short-circuit current behind the

relay. These temporization (30-50 ms was sufficient in present study) ensure that the relay measures stabilized voltages and currents once PE controls have reached 90% of their targets determined by the fault conditions.

- In order to ensure the correct behavior of faulted phase selection algorithms grid code requirements must be perfectly defined and applied by PE manufacturers, providing a response that could be easily modeled.

Further work should be carried out to determine the influence of future grid codes including a negative sequence current requirement for other faulted phase selection algorithms considering different practical implementations in PE control strategies. More simulations including evolving and consecutive faults and resistive faults must be considered. Other neutral earthing systems different to directly connected to earth must be assessed.

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